

QUALITATIVE PLANKTON OF A MANAGED AND UNMANAGED POND OF ANAIKKADU, THANJAVUR DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

A. Kavitha Amirthanayagi¹ K. Radhika² and S. Raveendran^{3*}

¹P.G. Department of Zoology, Kunthavai Naacchiyaar Government Arts College for Women (A), Thanjavur 613 007, Tamil Nadu, India

²P.G. Department of Zoology, Government Arts College for Women, Pudukkottai- 613007, Tamil Nadu, India

³P.G. Department of Zoology, Khadir Mohideen College, Adirampattinam-614 701, Tamil Nadu, India

Article History: Received 11th October 2016; 21st October 2016; Published 31st October 2016

ABSTRACT

The qualitative plankton of managed pond (pond 1) and unmanaged pond (pond 2) was studied in Anaikkadu, Thanjavur district. The study was undertaken on February first 2015. A total six classes of phytoplankton and three classes of zooplankton were recorded which contained 15 phytoplankton and twelve zooplankton species from both pond 1 and pond 2. Out of which eight species of phytoplankton and ten species of zooplankton were common at both the pond. Pond 1 alone had ten species of phytoplankton and twelve species of zooplankton. Pond 2 had fifteen species of phytoplankton and ten species of zooplankton. Pond 1 was richer in zooplankton and pond 2 was richer in phytoplankton. An inverse relationship was observed between phytoplankton and zooplankton abundance.

Keywords: Phytoplankton, Zooplankton, Plankton diversity, Plankton Net.

INTRODUCTION

Water is the base of life and development. The wetland forms unique biological freshwater ecosystem on the planet earth. These water bodies stores the freshwater form adjoining are during rainy season .It plays an important role in any ecosystem, hydrology of area and economy. They provide the habitats for migratory birds, aquaculture, plants, animals, planktons and microbes. Water is one of the major components of environmental resources (Usha *et al.*, 2006; Prithwiraj Jha *et al.*, 2008). Water is the necessity of life, without it there would be no life. Most of the biological reactions use water as the medium. Water is the habitat for a large number of aquatic organisms ranging from microscopic plankton to large aquatic animals and macrophytes. Moreover, there is a very close relationship between the metabolism of aquatic organisms and hydro biological parameters in a freshwater body (Mann *et al.*, 2003; Desmukh and Ambore, 2006).

In fresh water ecosystem phytoplanktonic and zooplanktonic organisms are important food sources for many aquatic animals specially fishes. The main for major carps like rohu, catla and their hybrids were found to be

planktonin origin (Mozumder and Naser, 2009). Plankton is a free floating organism, which is unable to maintain its distribution against water current. There are two types of planktonic organisms, namely phytoplankton and zooplanktons. Phytoplanktons are autotrophs; by zooplanktons depend on either photoplankton or other zooplanktons.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The qualitative plankton of a managed and unmanaged pond of Anaikkadu, Thanjavur was studied on first February 2016 are two ponds viz. A managed fish farm pond 1 and unmanaged pond 2. The pond 1 was used only for the purpose of culture of fish. Pond 2 was being used by villagers for multiple purposes. The collection of plankton was made by a net mode of bolting silk of 25 meshes with openings between the meshes 0.06mm squares. Since the dimensions of phytoplankton and zooplanktons are between 0.06 mm and 5 mm, the bolting silk No.25 was used. Each time plankton samples was collected by filtering about 200

*Corresponding Author: Dr. S. Raveendran, Associate Professor, Department of Zoology, Khadir Mohideen College, Adirampattinam 614 701, Tamil Nadu, India, Email: drs_r_kmc@rediffmail.com, Mobile: +91 9443617904.

liters of the surface water through the net. Immediately after collection of plankton, samples were preserved in 10 percent neutral formalin (one part of formalin diluted with three parts of distilled water adding a few drops of 10 percent NaOH). Plankton were observed under compound microscope and identified based on the keys for the identification of plankton. The identification of plankton species was done with the aid of plankton identification key and monographs by Needham and Needham (1962), and Battish (1992). Qualitative analysis was made using plankton counting chamber (Sedgewick Rafter counting Chamber).

RESULTS

The qualitative plankton of a managed and unmanaged pond is shown in tables 1 and 2. Four classes of phytoplankton (Cyanophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, Chlorophyceae and Xanthophyceae) were recorded from P1 and six classes (Cyanophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, Zygnemophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Zygnemophyceae and Xanthophyceae) were recorded from Pond 2. Ten species of phytoplankton (*Microcystis* sp., *Nostoc* sp., *Navicula* sp., *Synedra* sp., *Fragilaria* sp., *Eudorina* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Pediastrum* sp., *Oscillatoria* sp., and *Tribonema* sp.) were found in Pond 1 and fifteen species (*Microcystis* sp., *Nostoc* sp., *Eunotia* sp., *Navicula* sp., *Frustulia* sp., *Stauroneis* sp., *Fragilaria* sp., *Desmidium* sp., *Cosmarium* sp., *Closterium* sp., *Eudorina* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Oscillatoria* sp., *Spirogyra* sp. and *Tribonema* sp.) were found in Pond 2 (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of phytoplankton in unmanaged pond.

Class	Species Name	Distribution
Cyanophyceae	1. <i>Microcystis</i> sp., 2. <i>Nostoc</i> sp.,	Pond 1 & 2
Bacillariophyceae	3. <i>Eunotia</i> sp., 4. <i>Navicula</i> sp., 5. <i>Synedra</i> sp., 6. <i>Frustulia</i> sp., 7. <i>Fragilaria</i> sp., 8. <i>Stauroneis</i> sp.,	Pond 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 Pond 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 2
Chlorophyceae	9. <i>Eudorina</i> sp., 10. <i>Scenedesmus</i> sp., 11. <i>Pediastrum</i> sp., 12. <i>Oscillatoria</i> sp.	Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 Pond 1 & 2
Zygnemophyceae	13. <i>Desmidium</i> sp., 14. <i>Cosmarium</i> sp., 15. <i>Closterium</i> sp.,	Pond 2 Pond 2 Pond 2
Xanthophyceae	16. <i>Tribonema</i> sp.,	Pond 1 & 2
Zygnemophyceae	17. <i>Spirogyra</i> sp.,	Pond 2

Three classes (Rotifera, Branchiopoda, and Crustacea) of zooplankton were observed at both Pond 1 and Pond 2.

Twelve species of zooplankton (*Branchionus flucatus*, *Branchionus rubens*, *Branchionus caudatus*, *Branchionus filina*, *Angularis hiden* sp., *Daphnia* sp., *Moina* sp., *Cyclops* sp., *Mesocyclops* sp., *Microcyclops* sp., *Paracyclops* sp. and *Macrocyclops* sp.) were recorded from Pond 1 and Ten species (*Branchionus flucatus*, *Branchionus rubens*, *Branchionus caudatus*, *Branchionus filina*, *Daphnia* sp., *Moina* sp., *Macrothrix* sp., *Cyclops* sp., *Mesocyclops* sp. and *Paracyclops* sp.) were recorded from Pond 2 (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of zooplankton in unmanaged pond.

Class	Name of the Species	Distribution
Rotifera	1. <i>Branchionus flucatus</i> 2. <i>Branchionus rubens</i> 3. <i>Branchionus caudatus</i> 4. <i>Branchionus filina</i> , 5. <i>Branchionus Angularis</i>	Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1
Branchiopoda	6. <i>Daphnia</i> sp., 7. <i>Moina</i> sp., 8. <i>Macrothrix</i> sp.	Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 2
Crustacea	9. <i>Cyclops</i> sp., 10. <i>Mesocyclops</i> sp., 11. <i>Microcyclops</i> sp., 12. <i>Paracyclops</i> sp., 13. <i>Macrocyclops</i> sp.,	Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1 Pond 1 & 2 Pond 1

DISCUSSION

The qualitative plankton of a managed pond and unmanaged pond was studied in Anaikkadu, Thanjavur district. Phytoplankton forms the vital source of energy as primary producers and serves as a direct source of food to the other aquatic plants and animals (Battish, 1992). Among them eight species were found to be common at both the ponds. Ten species were recorded from Pond-1 and fifteen species were recorded from Pond-2. *Synedra* sp. and *Pediastrum* sp. was the species that were recorded only from Pond-1. *Eunotia* sp., *Frustulia* sp., *Stauroneis* sp., *Desmidium* sp., *Cosmarium* sp., *Closterium* sp. and *Spirogyra* sp. were the species that were recorded only from Pond 2 (Table 1). They are generally found in organic polluted waters (Sarwade and Kamble, 2006). Pond-2 was found to be richer in phytoplankton and showing eutrophic condition.

The paper deals with occurrence and biodiversity of phytoplankton. Occurrences of phytoplankton in four lakes were investigated in the month July, August and December, 2009. In these lakes 68 species of phytoplankton and 13 species of filamentous algae were recorded belonging to five major classes of algae namely Cyanophyceae, Euglenophyceae, Dinophyceae, and Bacillariophyceae (Leela *et al.*, 2010). As regards phytoplankton *Microcystis* sp. showed a diurnal pattern of decrease at day time and increase at night hours. These phytoplankton avoided strong lights and look shelter at the soil water inter-phase during day time and subsequently ascend to the surface at

night. This is an agreement with the findings of Petrucio and Barbosa (2004) and Melo *et al.* (2004).

In the present investigation *Nostoc punctiforme* were observed at 8 pm and 11 pm only. They were absent in the remaining period. So the *Nostoc punctiforme* did not show any distinct diel migration. This is in contrary to the findings of Banerjee (1967). *Oscillatoria tenuis* was found in abundant measure and their peak period of occurrence was at 2 am and minimum occurrence at 8 pm. This is in agreement with earlier worker (Melo *et al.*, 2004). Zooplankton are one of the most important biotic components influencing all the functional aspects of an aquatic ecosystem, such as food chains, food webs, energy flow and cycling of matter (Battish, 1992). Total Thirteen zooplanktons had been found from Pond 1 and Pond 2. Nine species were common at both the ponds. Twelve species were recorded from Pond 1 and ten species were recorded from Pond 2. *Angularis hidens*, *Microcyclops sp.*, and *Macrocyclops sp.* was the species that were only recorded from Pond 1. *Macrothrix sp.* was the species that were only recorded from Pond 2 (Table 2). Pond 1 was found to be richer in zooplankton. In the present investigation *Rotifera* were observed in pond 1 and pond 2. This is in contrary to the findings of Ahmad and Singh (1993). The present investigation is in agreement with the findings of Michael (1996) with regard to some species of rotifer. In the present investigation Branchipoda were observed in pond 1 and pond 2. This finding is agreement with the reports of Verma *et al.* (1987) and Ahamed and Singh (1993). Among zooplankton components Crustacea copepods were numerically abundant. In the present investigation crustacea copepods were observed in pond 1 and pond 2. This report is similar to the earlier workers (Ahamad and Singh, 1993; Murugan and Angelo Irudayasamy, 1996). In the present study Pond 2 was found to be richer in phytoplankton. Pond 1 was found to be richer in zooplankton.

CONCLUSIONS

An inverse relationship was observed between phytoplankton and zooplankton abundance. The managed fish culture pond which was periodically limed manure and fertilized showed greater planktonic diversity, with zooplankton being the dominant group. Whereas the unmanaged pond showed a less diverse and eutrophic condition, with phytoplankton being the dominant group. It implies that a large amount of ecological niches are remaining void and unutilized in unmanaged ponds. Whereas all the available ecological niches are being effectively utilized by the stocked fishes and periodically replenished by fertilization in the managed fish culture pond. Therefore selective stocking with appropriate species at low densities and extensive fish culture practices in the unmanaged ponds has ample scope. Adoption and transformation of such unmanaged ponds by scientific management practice into semi intensive fish culture ponds

may prove to be an ecologically efficient, financially feasible and socially viable venture.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Principal and Head of the Department of Zoology, Khadir Mohideen College, Adirampattinam for providing facilities to carry out the work.

REFERENCES

- Ahamed, S.H. and Singh A.K., 1993. Studied the correlation physico-chemical factors and zooplankter during diurnal variation in a fresh water tank at Phoil Bihar, India. *Environ. Biol.*, 14(2), 059-105.
- Banerjee, S.M., 1967. Water quality and soil condition of fish ponds in some states of India in relation to fish production. *Indian J. Fish.*, 14, 115-144.
- Battish, S.K. 1992. Freshwater zooplankton of India. Published by oxford and IBH publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Deshmukh, J.U. and Ambrose, N.E., 2006. Seasonal variations in physical aspects of pollution in Gadavari river a Nanded, Maharashtra, India. *J. Aqua. Biol.*, 21(2), 93-96.
- Leela, J., Bhosale Surekha., N., Dhumal and Anjali, B. Sabale., 2010. Phytoplankton Diversity of in four lakes of Satara District, Maharashtra State. *J. Biosci.*, 5(3), 449-454.
- Mann, N.K., Banerjee, S. and Bhowmik, M.L., 2003. Hydrobiology of wastewater-fed man-made lotic fish culture ponds in relation to pollution: Physico-chemical characteristics. *Philippine J. Sci.*, 132(1), 47-58.
- Melo. S., Huszar., V.L.M., Rolard, I., Esteveessr, F.A. and Bozelli., 2004. Phytoplankton diel variation and vertical distribution in two Amazonian flood plain lakes with different mixing regimes, *Amazoniana*, 18(1/2), 1-10.
- Michael, R.G., 1996. Diurnal variation in physic-chemical factors and zooplankton in the surface layers of three fresh water fish pond. *Indian J. Fish.* 13, 48-82.
- Mozumder, P.K. and Naser, M.N., 2009. Food and feeding habit of (*Catla catla* Ham.) and *Catla-rohu* hybrids. Bangladesh, *J. Zool.*, 37(2), 303-312.
- Murugan, S. and Angelo Irudayasamy, J. 1996. A comparative study of diurnal variations in some hydro biological conditions of a lake and tank at Maduranthakam. *J. Ecobiol.*, 8, 285-292.
- Needham, J.G. and Needham, P.R., 1962. To guide to the study of freshwater biology. Holden-Day inc. Sanfrancisco Costable and Co. Ltd., London. Pal Singh Publ., Dehradun, India, pp .94.

- Petrucio, M.M. and Barbosa, F.A.R., 2004. Diel variation of phytoplankton and bacterio plankton production rates in four tropical lakes, *Hydrobiologia*, 513, 71-76.
- Prithwiraj Jha, Sudip Barat, and Chitta R. Nayak, 2008. Fish production, water quality and bacteriological parameters of koi carp ponds under live. Food and Manure Based Management Regimes, 29(2), 165-173.
- Sarwade, A.B. and Kamble, N.A., 2006. Plankton diversity in Krishna river, Sangli Maharashtra. *J. Ecol. Nat. Environ.*, 6(4), 174-181.
- Usha, R., Ramalingam, K., and Bharathi, U.D., 2006. Freshwater lakes – A potential source for aquaculture activities – A model study on Perumal lake, Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu. *J. Environ. Biol.*, 27(4), 713-722.
- Verma, P.K., and Dalta Munshi, J.S., 1987. Plankton community structure of Badua reservoir, Bhagalpur, Bihar. *Trop. Ecol.*, 28, 200-207.